

TEXTUAL AND HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF HASAN IKHFA ALIZADE AND THE WORK “THE HISTORY OF THE CITY OF SHUSHA”

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Abstract

This article examines the manuscript work *The History of the City of Shusha* by Hasan Ikhfa Alizade, who lived in the early 20th century, from both a textual and historical perspective. Hasan Ikhfa Alizade, whose life and works have not been extensively studied until now, is analyzed through available archival materials and manuscript sources, highlighting his literary and scholarly profile. The first section of the study focuses on the codicological and paleographic features of the manuscript, including the type of script, paper, ink, page layout, and other aspects related to the copying process.

Subsequently, based on the historical data contained in the manuscript, the administrative, social, and cultural structure of 19th-century Shusha is analyzed. The study examines the city's administrative institutions, educational structures, religious sites, and social relations as described by Alizade, situating the work within the broader tradition of local historiography. Additionally, the reliability of the historical information in the text is assessed through a comparative analysis with other contemporary written sources.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that *The History of the City of Shusha* is an important resource both for the history of the text itself and for the historiography of local Azerbaijani history. It emphasizes Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's role in preserving the historical and cultural memory of 19th-century Shusha, providing valuable insights into the city's past through the lens of a rarely studied manuscript.

Keywords: Hasan Ikhfa Alizade, Shusha, textual, urban historiography, Karabagh.

Introduction

The nineteenth and twentieth centuries constituted a significant stage in the development of Azerbaijani literature. These periods are regarded as time frames marked by transition and transformation, representing a shift to a new phase in social, political, and literary-philosophical terms. During these eras, literature underwent substantial innovations in both form and content, laying the groundwork for the aesthetic reflection of public enlightenment, national awakening, and ideals of freedom.

In the nineteenth century, the emergence of new genres in Azerbaijani literature - such as the novel, long story, novella, short story, and drama - had a profound impact on the structure and content of classical literature and paved the way for the formation of new literary schools. Enriched by Enlightenment thought, the literature of this period began to take shape within the aesthetic and artistic framework of realism. Whereas romantic tendencies had predominated in the poetry of earlier periods, this phase brought Enlightenment ideas, a critical approach, and socio-political thought to the forefront. Consequently, literature that transcended the boundaries of classical poetry entered a new stage of development.

According to scholars, the principal ideological orientation of this period was Enlightenment thought, while its aesthetic and artistic tendency was Enlightenment realism. However, in literary studies, until the 1960s this phase was generally characterized as the period of critical realism (Habibbeyli, 2018, p. 4). According to Academician Isa Habibbeyli, nineteenth-century Azerbaijani literature completed its historical phase with the maturation and full development of Enlightenment-realist traditions; these traditions were also

sustained at the beginning of the twentieth century, thereby providing a basis for the preservation of the principle of continuity (Habibbeyli, 2004, pp. 5-6).

Elements of realism in Azerbaijani literature first appeared in the eighteenth century in the poetry of Molla Panah Vagif, and in the nineteenth century they developed in the form of Enlightenment realism in the works of Mirza Fatali Akhundzade. At the beginning of the twentieth century, with the laying of the foundations of critical realism by Jalil Mammadguluzade, this tendency acquired new content and form. According to Prof. Dr. Teyyar Salamoğlu, critical realism emerged as the stage of realism following Enlightenment realism; the works of the artists gathered around the journal *Molla Nasreddin* shaped a type of critical realism that represented an entirely new qualitative phase in Azerbaijani realism (Salamoğlu, 2018, p. 9).

Mir Jalal Pashayev, in turn, defines this period as the “literature of the Molla Nasreddin era” (Mir Jalal, 2004, p. 15). The journal *Molla Nasreddin* made a significant contribution not only to satirical (satire/humor) literature but also to the development of the national Enlightenment movement and social thought; it brought together intellectuals from various professional backgrounds, including teachers, writers, painters, and musicians. For this reason, the figures active within this intellectual milieu have been referred to in the scholarly literature as the “Molla Nasreddinists.”

One of the representatives of this intellectual circle was Hasan Ikhfa Alizade, a writer who was educated in Shusha, Karabakh. Alizade is recognized in Azerbaijani literature as a playwright and poet, as well as a historian and regional researcher (geographer/local historian). The author of numerous works written in a realist

style, Alizade reflected Enlightenment ideas and the social shortcomings of his time in his writings through a critical perspective. Among his Enlightenment activities, his pedagogical work occupies a particularly important place; he taught in schools in Aghjabadi, Aghdam, and Shusha. These factors make it possible to regard him as one of the prominent representatives of Enlightenment realism.

The work entitled *The History of the City of Shusha*, which we have transcribed, occupies an important place in the literary profile of Hasan Ikhfa Alizade. In this work, the author provides a comprehensive depiction of the historical development of the city of Shusha, as well as its social, economic, architectural, and cultural life. Of particular significance for the field of urban historiography, this study also demonstrates that Shusha was one of the cities constructed in a planned manner. The city was surrounded by fortification walls and distinguished by its stone-paved streets and neighborhood-based urban structure. The presence of a mosque, a bathhouse, and a marketplace in each neighborhood serves as an indicator of the city's social organization and system of public life.

Shusha functioned as an important economic center in terms of craftsmanship, carpet weaving, silk production, and trade. At the same time, a rich cultural environment emerged in the fields of music, literature, and Enlightenment thought. Artists such as Uzeyir Hajibeyli, Jabbar Garyaghdiohlu, Khan Shushinski, and Bulbul were among the prominent figures nurtured by this milieu. The schools, madrasas, and literary assemblies operating in the city played a crucial role in the development of Enlightenment ideals. In this context, the activities of figures such as Khurshidbanu Natavan, Mir Mohsun Navvab, Abdurrahim Bey Hagverdiyev, and Yusif Vazir Chamanzaminli deserve particular emphasis.

Through this work, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade opened a new direction in the field of Azerbaijani urban historiography, using the city of Shusha as a case study.

The Life of Hasan Ikhfa Alizade

One of the most reliable sources on the life and literary activity of Hasan Ikhfa Alizade is an autobiographical text written in his own hand. According to the information provided in this document, Alizade was born in 1893 in the city of Shusha. His father, Zeynalabdin, was known in Shusha by the nickname Aşpazbaşı (chief cook) and was illiterate. Nevertheless, he made considerable efforts to ensure that his son received an education. Hasan Ikhfa completed his primary education in his native city and began his professional career as a teacher in 1916.

From his secondary school years onward, Alizade began composing various poems and satirical texts, through which he criticized certain individuals. His acquaintance with the journal Molla Nasreddin occurred coincidentally; his first satirical poem, entitled "Bakıdan Ərəbski artist cavan gəldi, Guya Şuşaya birdən dünyanı alan gəldi" (A young Arabsky artist came from Baku, As if he had suddenly come to conquer the whole world in Shusha) was published in the journal in 1910. Jalil Mammadguluzade appreciated the poem and presented him with works by Pushkin; this

encouragement gave impetus to Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's literary activities. Consequently, Alizade became one of the regular contributors to the journal Molla Nasreddin for many years.

In 1914, upon the official invitation of Jalil Mammadguluzade, he went to Tiflis and joined the editorial board of the journal. In addition to Molla Nasreddin, he published writings under the pseudonyms "Mirza Goshuneli," "Mirzeli," and "Hemin Humen" in satirical periodicals such as Kelniyyet, Mezeli, and Seda. He also served as the editor of the children's magazine Birinci Gedom.

In 1923, with the aim of continuing his education, he was admitted to the Azerbaijan Pedagogical University and graduated in 1927. In the following years, he worked as a teacher in various regions, serving in pedagogical institutions, an agricultural vocational school, and secondary schools. After being appointed to the Aghjabadi district in 1946, he encountered various difficulties, which he did not hesitate to express in his satirical poems. His relations with the district Party committee's second secretary and the Head of the Department of Public Education became strained; these officials, emphasizing his alleged inadequacy, arranged for him to undergo a written examination in order to "prove" his professional incompetence.

Hasan Ikhfa recounted this incident in his poems with an ironic tone as follows: "This man summoned me and dictated a spelling exercise at the level of the third grade of primary school, saying, 'My boy, it turns out you have no education.' When the exercise proved to be correct, he became embarrassed and said, 'Well, no - seems you do know something after all...'"

One of the satirical poems he dedicated to the officials of that period:

"Berekallah, maşallah, aferin raykom bala,
Lazımı suretdə var imiş ihtiraetin senin,
Nögteyi-Ağcabedi seyınle nurlandı aceb,
Bu Kebirli halqımı alim edib, zətın senin."

(Berekallah, maşallah, well done, young man of the district committee,

Your inventions evidently exist in the proper measure;

The Aghjabadi point has been illuminated by your actions, astonishingly,

You have made the people of Kebirli learned; it is thanks to you.)

Regarding the Head of Public Education, he composed the following verses:

"Yokdur savadım benim, neyleyim Güller hanım?

Dahi cezana gelib tenelerinden canım,
Acizim, ey acizim, bir iş gelmir elimden,
Bir kes eşitmez o cür remzli söz dilimden,
Bisavadam, bisavad, biclik ile yok işim,
Bu sebebe galmayıb şimdi ağızda dişim."

(I have no education, what can I do, Lady Güller? Alas, my soul suffers from your rebukes.

I am helpless, oh helpless, nothing comes from my hands,

No one can understand such symbolic words from my tongue.

I am unlettered, unlettered, my work is gone with ignorance,

For this reason, my teeth now remain untouched in my mouth)

After his assignment in the Aghjabadi district, he was appointed to the Aghdam district, where he continued his teaching activities and periodically published articles in the newspaper Lenin Yolu.

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade passed away in 1972. His grave is located in the “Mirze Hasan” cemetery in his native city of Shusha.

The Works of Hasan Ikhfa Alizade

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade’s rich literary legacy encompasses theatrical works, stories, poems, translations, articles, letters, and historical texts written in various genres. A significant portion of his works is preserved at the National Archive of the Republic of Azerbaijan and at the M. Fuzuli Manuscripts Institute of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences.

Materials comprising 18 files have been collected at the National Archive. This collection includes not only the author’s works but also various photographs, official documents, and draft copies of some of his writings. The documents pertaining to Alizade have been classified according to two separate inventory lists: the first list, containing 870 items, was submitted to the Central State Archive of Literature and Art of the Azerbaijan SSR on 15 May 1970, while the second list, containing 10 items, was submitted on 10 October 1989. The first list covers the period 1914–1970, and the second list covers 1964–1966 (Göstərici, 2020, p. 306).

Among the manuscripts preserved at the M. Fuzuli Manuscripts Institute of the ANAS are: *Mekr-i Zenan* (registration no. B-3354/4979), *Mektublar* (registration no. B-3360/4985), *Ziver ve Gonşuları* (registration no. B-3361/4986), *Melahet ve Letafet, Evlenmek* (registration no. B-3364/4989), *Ciddi Manzumeler* (registration no. B-3365/4990), and *The History of the City of Shusha* (registration no. B-4556/6181).

Theatrical Works

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade’s verse tragedy *Balahanım* consists of five acts and seven scenes. The work addresses the social and political events in the Karabakh region between 1914 and 1920, focusing on the peasants’ struggle against the oppression of local khans. The play foregrounds the village’s socio-economic conditions, Enlightenment ideas, post-revolutionary changes, the construction of a school building, and the exaltation of ideals of freedom.

The three-act musical *Mekr-i Zenan* was staged in 1917. The work critiques the main character, Molla İbrahim, for his lack of education and superstitious practices. A scene depicting the servant Ceferali’s property being reclaimed from Molla holds particular importance as a denunciation of such superstition. This work should not be confused with Ahmet Gemerli’s work of the same name. Alizade’s comedy is written with an Enlightenment-oriented stance, opposing religious fanaticism and ignorance.

The four-act operetta *Namerd-i Ruzigar* focuses on the critique of a miserly merchant. The main plot

revolves around Haji Semed’s behavior contrary to humanistic and family values and his subsequent loss of property to his debtor, Rzagulu. This work was staged in 1916.

In addition, stage works such as *Ferhad ve Şirin* (1915), the two-act comedy *Alesger*, and the one-act operetta *Muhammedali Sultanmecid Fegirleri* are also important examples of the author’s theatrical corpus.

Stories

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade compiled his stories in a notebook titled *Namus*. Among these are *Eshref ve Suleyman*, *Melahet ve Letafet*, *Bizim Necabetli Han*, and *Ahter Hanım ve Gonşuları*. The story *Ahter Hanım ve Gonşuları* has occasionally appeared in manuscripts under the titles *Namuslu Qız* and *Ziver ve Gonşuları*. In addition, a separate story entitled *Evlenmek* is also preserved.

Poems and Translations

Alizade’s poetic legacy includes numerous works such as *Tahmis-i Füzuli*, *Oturag*, *Ele Düşdü*, *Dolaşma*, *Sahib-i Ali*, *Bak*, *Akşam*, *Deliyem*, *Garğa ve Balığ*, *Behr-i Tevil*, *Ruh-i Revanım Ahmed*, and *Banla Daha*. He also translated several rubai by Baba Tahir Uryan from Persian into Azerbaijani, preparing accompanying lexical and terminological notes. Additionally, the author compiled various riddles, bayati (folk couplets), and proverbs, organizing them alphabetically.

Historical Works

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade’s most significant historical studies are *The History of the City of Shusha* and its continuation, *The Historical Monuments of the City of Shusha*. In *The History of the City of Shusha*, the author focuses on the political and cultural past of the city and indicates at the conclusion of the work that he intends to prepare a separate study on its historical monuments (*Alizade 12a*).

To this end, he compiled a separate notebook entitled *The Historical Monuments of the City of Shusha*, although this notebook remains incomplete. In it, Alizade provides detailed information about the Khan’s Divankhane, the arsenal, the prison, as well as various mosques and caravanserais in Shusha, noting that some of these structures have since disappeared.

A notable feature of this work is the inclusion of inscriptions from the Juma Mosque (*Yukhari Masjid*), *Ashaghi Masjid*, and *Mescid-i Aksay-i Huseyniyya*, presented along with their translations from Persian into Azerbaijani Turkish.

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade’s Work the History of the City of Shusha

The manuscript entitled *The History of the City of Shusha*, registered under archival number B 4556/6181 at the M. Fuzuli Manuscripts Institute of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, belongs to Hasan Ikhfa Alizade. The work consists of two notebooks, each measuring approximately 17.5 × 20.5 cm, and is preserved in a light gray cardboard folder.

The text was copied in 1960 into an ordinary school notebook, written in a tahriri hand with purple ink. The headings within the manuscript are written in different colored pens—red, green, blue, brown, and orange.

The work opens with a poetic introduction by the author, beginning with the following couplets:

Zahid, deme: dünya ne senindir, ne benim!
Sen sevmediğin cümle bu yerler vatanımdır.
Vermem vatanın bir karışın yadlara asla,
Şefkatli anamdır, bu benim besleyenimdir.

(O ascetic, do not say: the world belongs neither to you nor to me!

All these lands, which you do not love, are my homeland.

I will never give an inch of the homeland to strangers;

It is my compassionate mother; it is she who nurtures me.)

Following the poem, the notebook contains the Introduction and Preface sections. After the preface, which presents the author's general reflections on the city of Shusha, the main text of the work begins. The first notebook covers historical events between 1747 and 1805, while the second notebook addresses the period from 1805 to 1923.

Notebook I is divided by the author into three main sections. At the beginning of each section, there is a kind of table of contents reflecting its content:

Section I – Introduction:

“Brief information on the state, administrative structure, and construction activities of the Karabakh Khanate before the foundation of the city of Shusha”

Preface (by the author)

Who is Panah Khan? (origin and lineage)

Panah Khan's construction activities:

- Bayat Fortress
- Shah Bulagi (Ternegut) Fortress

Section II – The City of Shusha:

Discussions and decisions

Construction of the city (naming, administrative organization, and laws)

Architectural structure of the city

Geographical location of Shusha

Section III – Historical Events (Panah Khan Period):

The attack and defeat of Muhammad Hasan Khan Qajar

The betrayal and hostility of Georgian Prince Irakli II; assistance of Haji Chelebi

The attack, defeat, strategy, and consequences of Fathali Khan Afshar

In this section of the manuscript, the author attempts to narrate historical events in a literary style, occasionally including poetic excerpts.

Notebook II serves as a logical continuation of the first notebook and is likewise organized into three main sections:

Section IV – Russian Empire Period (1805–1917)

Section V – Shusha After the Treaty of Turkmenchay (1828–1917)

Section VI – Events of 1918–1920 and the Burning of Shusha.

The work presents the historical development stages of the city of Shusha from the author's nationally conscious and patriotic perspective, addressing political events alongside architectural and cultural contexts in detail. This manuscript is considered a valuable

source that unites Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's literary and historical perspectives.

In the History of the City of Shusha, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade pays attention not only to political and military developments but also to the scientific, cultural, and artistic life of the city. The author mentions the names of several prominent poets, writers, and musicians who lived in Shusha and provides examples from their works. These details demonstrate that the city's history is rich not only politically but also culturally and spiritually.

In preparing the work, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade relied on various historical sources. According to his own account, the foundational references included Mirza Jamal Javanshir's History of Karabakh, Mirza Adigozal Bey's Karabaghname, Abbasgulu Agha Bakikhanov's Gulistan-i Irem, Mehmed Hasan Bey Baharly's History of Azerbaijan, and Rashid Bey Ismailov's History of Azerbaijan, along with History of Iran, History of the Caucasus, and several other sources (Alizade, 1960, p. 4a).

In addition, the author approached certain sources with a critical perspective. In particular, he evaluated Ahmed Bey Javanshir's work as insufficient and biased, stating: "In the recently acquired small booklet entitled 'Âsâr-ı Ahmed Bey' (not yet published), we read quite interesting accounts. Even if this book were to be published, it cannot be considered valuable because it was written under the influence of two different factors" (Alizade, 1960, p. 38a).

At the same time, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade also drew directly on oral sources. He indicates that he relied on information provided by a man named Meshadi Ali, who lived in Shusha and had reached over 100 years of age. Meshadi Ali offered the author certain details about the history of Karabakh and stated that, although he did not personally witness events such as the deaths of Molla Panah Vagif and Mehmed Bey, he had learned about them from his elders (Alizade, 1960, pp. 37b, 38a).

The section of the work covering the years 1905–1920 is based directly on the author's personal observations. Having witnessed the social and political developments of this period, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade describes the events drawing on his own experiences.

Although the author drew on previously written Karabagnames, he disagreed with certain views and therefore decided in 1960 to compose The History of the City of Shusha as an independent work. By that time, Mirza Adigozal Bey's Karabaghname (1950) and Mirza Jamal Javanshir's History of Karabakh (1959) had already been published.

Alizade wished for his work to be published and, for this purpose, prepared it in two notebooks and submitted it in 1960 to the History Institute of the Azerbaijan SSR Academy of Sciences. The manuscript, examined by the institute, was deemed unsuitable for publication. Consequently, in 1961, the author appealed to the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Azerbaijan SSR. On his initiative, a commission was established to evaluate the work, and Hasan Ikhfa Alizade personally participated in these deliberations.

The commission members concluded that the work was generally not suitable for publication; however, considering the author's effort and some valuable historical information contained in the manuscript, they decided to pay him an honorarium of 100 manat and to preserve the work in the institute's archive.

This episode reflects not only Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's scholarly and historical legacy but also the official attitude of the period and the inherent limitations of the publishing policies of that time.

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's work *The History of the City of Shusha* was first published in summarized form in the third volume of the *Karabagnames* compilation, which appeared in 2006. This three-volume collection was prepared for publication by Nazim Ahundov and Akif Ferzeliyev, systematically organizing and presenting *Karabagnames* authored by various writers. In this edition, materials from Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's personal archive, preserved at the National Archive Department of the Republic of Azerbaijan, were utilized. However, it should be noted that these documents were not systematically organized, were often in draft form, and were found in a disordered state.

The notebooks written in the author's own hand and preserved at the Mehmed Fuzuli Manuscripts Institute of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences had not previously been the subject of scholarly study. In this work, they are presented for the first time and made accessible to the public.

In the introduction to his work, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade expresses his profound sense of belonging to the city of Shusha and his love for the homeland in a highly literary style:

"Shusha! How dear, native, gentle, and beloved a name, how beautiful and kind a mother - 'Homeland,' how enchanting a place that it has always been my most sacred duty to kneel before this beautiful name and respectfully kiss the 'earth beneath it,' and for its sake to give up everything - life, property, existence, and more; to be stained with red blood, to perish - this has been for me the most sacred happiness and honorable state" (Alizade, 1960, p. 3a).

In his work, the author emphasizes that, despite its geographically small area, Shusha became a leading cultural center in the South Caucasus from the second half of the 19th century onward. He highlights the city's influence in literature, music, and the arts, noting that the intellectuals, poets, teachers, and artists raised there were distinctly distinguished from those in other regions of Azerbaijan.

A defining feature that sets Hasan Ikhfa Alizade apart from previous *Karabagnames* authors is his holistic approach to historical periods. Alizade documents not only the khanate era and Tsarist Russia but also the Soviet period, particularly recording the provocations and tragic events carried out by Armenian armed groups in 1905 and 1918.

The author states his purpose in the work as follows: "In this small work, I will record the joyful and prosperous days that our Shusha has experienced from the day its first cornerstone was laid (1747) until today, as well as its painful, unfortunate, sorrowful, and tragic periods" (Alizade, 1960, p. 4b).

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade cites different dates regarding the founding of the city of Shusha. On page 16a of the manuscript, it is noted that the city's foundations were laid in 1752 and that the urbanization process was completed in 1754; however, on page 18b, the founding date is directly given as 1754. In the introduction, the date is recorded as 1747. This discrepancy likely arises from the author's consideration of the establishment of the Karabakh Khanate separately from Shusha's formation as an administrative center.

For comparison, in the first volume of the *Karabagnames* compilation, citing Mirza Adigozal Bey, the foundation of Shusha is stated to have occurred at the end of 1751 or the beginning of 1752 (*Karabagnames*, p. 48). In Tofiq Mustafazade's work *The Karabakh Khanate*, it is indicated that the foundations of Shusha Fortress were laid in 1753 - 1754, and the construction was completed in 1756 - 1757 (Mustafazade, 2005, p. 39).

When composing *The History of the City of Shusha*, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade relied not only on written sources but also on oral testimonies. He considered information obtained from a man named Meshadi Ali, who had lived in Shusha for over a century, as an important source. This informant admitted that he had not personally witnessed events such as the deaths of Molla Panah Vagif and Mehmed Bey, but shared what he had learned from the elders of his time. Events covering the years 1905 - 1920, however, are documented directly based on the author's own personal observations.

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's *The History of the City of Shusha* is not merely a historical chronicle; it is also a valuable scholarly work that reflects the author's national consciousness, literary imagination, and extensive use of source material. His contribution to the *Karabagnama* tradition can be regarded as a significant resource for both historiography and cultural heritage within the scientific and ideological frameworks of his era.

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's work begins with the political activities of Panah Khan. The author notes that during the formation of the khanate, Panah Khan commissioned the construction of the Bayat and Shahbulak fortresses and later issued coins in his name, called "Penahabad" and "Penavat." These details demonstrate the author's effort to address not only the political process but also the economic and monetary aspects in a comprehensive manner.

The author also provides a notable etymological explanation regarding the name of Shusha. According to him, the city's name is linked to the village of "Shushu." Initially, this settlement was called "Shushu Fortress" or "Shushu City," which over time became "Shushi." Subsequently, the expression "Shahr-i Shushi" became common; this form evolved first into "Shushe," then under Persian influence into "Shishe," and finally stabilized in Azerbaijani Turkish as "Shusha." The author supports this linguistic development with examples from classical poetry.

Şehri-Şişe ki, aceb âb u havası dâred,
Hurram onki baserî-kûyi o câyi dâred.

(The city of Shishe possesses such wondrous water and air,

Its streets and alleys are lively and full of charm).

- M.Q.H.-Vefa

Şişede, Şirvan'da vurur tek sebir. (in Shishe, one sneezes, as in Shirvan).

- M.A.Sabir (Alizade, 1960, s.12b).

These couplets are presented as examples supporting the etymology proposed by the author regarding the historical and literary use of the toponym "Shusha."

In the section on architecture, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade notes that the general structure of Shusha reflects the style of Iranian architecture. However, this view is scientifically debatable. Contemporary research shows that Shusha's architecture primarily embodies local architectural traditions specific to the Karabakh region. While this style incorporates elements of Eastern architecture, it is enriched by local construction techniques and decorative features.

One of the leading representatives of this architectural school was the architect Kerbelayi Sefihan Karabagi. The Lower Govhar Agha Mosque (1889 - 1890), madrasas, neighborhood mosques, mansions, baths, and other structures he built in Shusha are considered among the pinnacles of Karabakh architecture. Kerbelayi Sefihan demonstrated exceptional skill in combining the classical constructive elements of Eastern architecture with local materials and architectural styles (azerbaijan-news.az).

The architectural features and general cityscape of Shusha were also documented by travelers and visitors in the 19th century. For example, some articles published in the Kavkaz newspaper describe the city as follows: "Among the various houses and residences in the city, the mansions inhabited by members of the khan's family immediately attract attention: these structures possess a distinctive character. They are surrounded by high walls with circular towers at the corners" (Gazeta Kavkaz, 1857).

Hasan Ikhfa Alizade's work *The History of the City of Shusha* is not limited to the chronological and political description of events; it also provides valuable information on the city's cultural, ethnographic, and architectural heritage. At times, the author's assessments, based on personal observations and local accounts, make this work a significant source for both historical research and the study of intellectual history.

In his manuscript *The History of the City of Shusha*, Hasan Ikhfa Alizade provides a detailed and locally enriched description of the city's geographical location. According to the author, Shusha is bordered to the south by Jidir Plain, Uçmih hills, the Boyuk Dashalti stream, and Kirs Mountain; to the north by Dovteleb hill, Halifeli stream, Halifeli village, and the Mikhtoken mountain slope; to the west by the villages of Zarisli and Galaderesi, Turshsu, and Sagsaganli Mountain; and to the east by Shushakend, Bagirgan (or Bağirkhan) Mountain, Topkhana forest, and Hazine rock (Alizade, 1960, p.14a). This geographic framing demonstrates that the work is also a valuable resource for local history and topography.

At the end of the first notebook, the author transitions to topics of science, culture, literature, and art, presenting biographical information about some poets who lived in Shusha and including examples of their

poetry. For instance, a poem written by Ağabeyim Ağa of the Khan family expresses his longing for Karabakh:

Men aşikem, Karabağ,

Yağışa bak, kara bak,

Tehran cennete dönse,

Yaddan çıkmaz, Karabağ.

(I am a lover, Karabakh,

Look at the rain, look at the snow,

Even if Tehran turns into paradise,

It will never be forgotten, Karabakh).

"Ağabeyim Ağa Jevanşir, the aunt of Khurshudbanu Natavan (d. 1897), one of Azerbaijan's esteemed intellectuals, gained renown in Karabakh for his beauty, eloquence, diplomatic skills, and especially his poetic talent" (Rahimova, 2024, p.1030).

This perspective demonstrates that the author approaches history not only from political and military aspects but also from a cultural standpoint.

The second notebook consists of three main sections:

IV – The Russian Empire Period (1805–1917),

V – Shusha After the Treaty of Turkmenchay (1828–1917),

VI – Selected Events (1918–1920).

In this notebook, the author records historical developments up to 1923, giving particular emphasis to the destruction carried out by Armenian armed groups against Azerbaijani Turks in 1918. At the end of the work, he returns to Shusha's achievements in culture, music, and the arts, providing information on the creations of various artists and musicians.

Nevertheless, some historical details in the text lack precision. For instance, on page 19b, Talish Melik, Melik Usub, one of the Hamse rulers, is erroneously identified as the Melik of Chilebord (Alizade, 1960, p.19b). Additionally, the association of Shusha's architectural style with Iranian architecture (Alizade, 1960, p.13a) and the transcription of the famous tar player Sadıqjan's name as "Sadıqja" are other inconsistencies. Such errors likely reflect the author's limited access to archival sources at the time and the reliance on oral accounts for some information.

When uncertain about certain details, Alizade marks these entries with parentheses and question marks. This practice indicates that the author approached some information with caution, possibly intending future verification, or leaving the judgment to the reader. Examples of such uncertainties include the date of Panah Khan's death, İbrahim Khan's stance toward the Russians, and the exaggerated depiction of some events (Alizade, p.21a).

Conclusion

In the third volume of the compilation *Karabağnameler*, Nazim Ahundov, who prepared this work for publication, notes that many Azerbaijani intellectuals attempted to write the history of Karabakh during the 19th century and the early 20th century. He emphasizes the significance of these publications, mentioning Hasan Ikhfa Alizade by name, both in terms of historical interest and as evidence of the deep attention Azerbaijani intellectuals paid to the history of the Karabakh Khanate (Karabağnameler, 2006, p.184).

Hasan İkhfa Alizade's approach to events largely stems from his perspective as a literary figure and cultural promoter. He often presents historical events in a narrative style, drawing on the techniques of storytelling. One aspect that makes his work particularly valuable is that the author personally witnessed certain events, describing them in the first person. Alizade aimed to provide a comprehensive and multifaceted panorama, encompassing not only political history but also the socio-cultural, literary, and architectural heritage of Shusha. This characteristic renders his work a valuable resource not only for historiography but also for cultural studies and urban history.

References

1. Ədəbiyyat və mətbuat xadimlərinin şəxsi mənşəli arxiv fondlarının göstəricisi. (2020). Index of personal archival fonds of literary and press figures. Bilim ve Eğitim Yayınları.
2. Alizade, H. İ. (1960). History of the city of Shusha (Manuscript No. B 4556/6181). Institute of Manuscripts named after M. Fuzuli, Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences.
3. Alizade, H. İ. (1945–1950). Historical monuments of the city of Shusha (Archival fond F.510, op. 1). National Archives Administration of Azerbaijan.
4. Gazeta Kavkaz. (1857). No. 58, Tiflis.
5. Habibbeyli, İ. (2004). Azerbaijani writers in the early twentieth century. Nurlan.
6. Habibbeyli, İ. (2018). The enlightenment movement and the period of enlightenment realism in Azerbaijani literature (19th century). Bilim ve Eğitim Yayınları.
7. Halilli, Ş. (2024). Hasan İhfa Alizade and the work "Monuments of the City of Shusha." In A. Aytaç (Ed.), Proceedings of the 18th International Symposium on Turkish Culture, Art and the Protection of Cultural Heritage (pp. 375–378). Komrat, Gagauzia–Moldova.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/387494581>
8. Halilli, Ş. (2022). Paleography. In F. Halilli (Ed.), Shusha: Study of the historical and cultural heritage (pp. 82–98). Bilim ve Eğitim Yayınları.
<https://doi.org/10.30546/978-9952-8412-3-7.03>
9. Karabaknamehs. (2006). N. Axundov & A. Ferzeliyev (Eds.), 3 vols. Bilim ve Eğitim Yayınları.
10. Mir Jalal. (2004). Literary schools in Azerbaijan. Ziya-Nurlan.
11. Mustafazade, T. (2005). The Karabakh Khanate. Nurlar NPB.
12. Rahimova, L. (2024). The motif of exile in the poetry of Agha Javanşir and Heyran Khanum Dunbuli. Akademi Tarih ve Düşünce Dergisi, 11(2), 1025–1043.
13. Salamoğlu, T. (2018). The aesthetics of critical realism in Azerbaijan (in the context of the works of C. Mammadguluzade and M. E. Sabir). Orkhan Yayınları.